

Title: Older Adults Requirements in XR Cultural Heritage Exploration

Abstract:

As Extended Reality (XR) technologies become more prevalent in cultural heritage applications, there's a growing need to understand and cater to the specific requirements of older adult users. These technologies offer unique opportunities for engagement, yet the challenge lies in ensuring these experiences are accessible and meaningful to older adults, who may have different requirements, needs and preferences than younger users.

This paper presents a comprehensive exploration of older adults' needs within XR environments, with a focus on cultural heritage experiences. Employing a mix of social research methods, including interviews and questionnaires, alongside innovative sensor-based technologies for data collection, this work aims to offer a detailed view of older adults' interactions with XR. The approach combines qualitative insights from personal stories and quantitative data from sensors like eye-tracking devices, providing a rich understanding of older adults' preferences, challenges, and expectations. This multifaceted analysis reveals key patterns in how older adults engage with XR, guiding the development of more inclusive and user-friendly XR applications in cultural heritage. The findings and methodologies outlined in this study not only enhance XR experiences for older adults but also serve as a model for future research in user-centered technology design.

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